

SOME GEOGRAPHICAL ASPECTS OF AL RIYADH

(SAUDI ARABIA)

BY

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PHYSICAL ENVIRONMENT

1. LOCATION.

Al Riyadh stands on the eastern bank of Wadi Hanifah, just south of the junction of Wadi Al Aysan and Wadi Hanifah. Moreover, Wadi Al Bat'ha runs on the east side of the town. Thus, it is situated at the confluence of three major arterial Wadis (Fig. 1).

The advantageous site of Al Riyadh on the east bank of Wadi Hanifah is greatly enhanced, as it stands on a point where the wadi has been enriched by water from its rich tributaries : Wadi Wubair and Wadi Qaddiyah north of Al Riyadh. In the mean time wadi Numar — one of the feeders of wadi Hanifah — runs direct south of al Riyadh.

Such a site helps the town to make use of the waters of wadi Hanifah as well as its other five tributaries. This wellendowed situation has given Al Riyadh its name which literally means a cluster of gardens, palm trees and other vegetation. Also this name is very significant when compared with the desert landscape all around.

The town lies on an eroded depression in the jurassic plateau, 1950 feet (594 meters) above sea-level, at the intersection of the north latitude $24^{\circ} 42'$ and the east longitude $46^{\circ} 44'$.

Riyadh Basin Complex :

Al Riyadh and the near villages, *i.e.* Manfuhah, Al-Dir'iyah and Al Ammariyah, form a basin which represents the oikoumene part of north eastern Najd. This basin was formerly called Al Arid. Al Kharj and the other villages of Al Yammamah, Al Sulaymaniyah, Al Salamiyah, Al

Ghanamiyah, Al Thulaymah, Al Hayatim, Al Mohamadi, Ad Dilam, and Na'jan, form another basin 80 kms to the south east of the former basin. In this basin many Wadis conflow; from the north and north-west, wadi As Sulayy, Wadi Al Haniyah and Wadi Hanifah flow to the basin; Wadi Nisah flow from the west; Ma'wan, Sha'ib As Sawt and Wadi Al Aqimi run to this basin from the south. From this basin Wadi Sahba runs to the East. This basin forms the oikoumene part of south eastern Najd. These two basins form Al Riyadh basin complex.

There is another territorial viewpoint to consider, the relative centrality of the town. Its location as a nuclear core among the component regions of the kingdom makes it weld the different administrative units.

It lies within equal distance from Al Qasim and Shammar on the north, and Al Aflaj and Al Dawasir on the south, or in other words, it lies half way between the sea-sand of Al-Nofud on the N. and the extensive sandy structure of Ar Rub' Al Khali on the south.

Also, Al Riyadh is situated in a proportionate distance between Al Ahsa on the Arab Gulf on the east, and Al Hijaz and Assir on the Red Sea, on the west.

Such well endowed position makes the town command the east west roads as well as the north south ones. Also the town is of nodal location on the axis of settlement belt in Eastern Najd, between Tuwaiq Mountains on the west and Aramah Plateau escarpments on the east.

Nowadays, Al Riyadh is vigorously advancing and so vastly flourishing that its importance outweighs all the other important towns of the Kingdom. This booming stage has been reached after oil was discovered and commercially produced in the Arab Gulf Region which is not far away from the town. Its present progress is partly due to the role which the town is undertaking as the seat of government.

2. THE GEOLOGICAL CONFINES.

The town has been built on an eroded elongated depression in the Upper Jurassic deposits, mainly Arab and Jubaila Limestone formation ⁽¹⁾.

⁽¹⁾ Geologic Map 1-207 A of the Northern Tuwayq Quadrangle; Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. Washington, 1958.

Fig. 1.

These formations include brown and tan limestone, calcarenite, and dolomite, usually distributed and in places brecciated by solution collapse. The Sold Jurassic limestone crops out in many places in and outside the town. East of the town, Lower cretaceous deposits spread, mainly of cream and tan compact limestone with infrequent thin calcarenite and coquina layers. These cretaceous deposits form some sort of escarpments, *i.e.* separated low rocky hills east of the new spreading out town.

The depression is embedded with silt, sand, gravel and other units of Quaternary age. Wadi Hanifah and its torrential feeders mainly brought the fine sediments to the depression.

Silt and sand, from the depression bed, were the only materials which the people of Al Riyadh, used to build their old time homes. Such a fact means that the old inhabitants of the town lacked the means of cutting stones from the near by rock hills to be used building materials.

The alluvial deposits in the depression made a good soil for the green belt of date grove to flourish and encompass the old walled town. Also these old deposits serve as a reservoir for the rain water to accumulate and to be kept away from being evaporated under the scorching heat of the sun in such a dry region. Thus wells dug in big houses or in every group of small houses met the limited domestic needs of the old inhabitants. These wells sunk in the depression bed are from 10 to 15 meters deep.

3. WATER RESOURCES.

The wells sunk in the depression bed, in the old houses of the old town, are diminishing in number and importance; many clay houses have been demolished to make way for the new modern buildings of western architecture. Such mansions make use of the pipes bringing water from the pumping station of Al Ha'ir. Also the water pipes knew their way to many of the old clay houses. But other wells, sunk in the depression bed, in the new Riyadh are still working by mechanical pumps to cover a part of the domestic needs of the new town, and help the water source of Al Ha'ir to meet a great part of the needs of the huge area of Modern Riyadh.

The present network of pipes that cover Al Riyadh, takes its water from two localities in Wadi Hanifah. The permeable gravel bed of this wadi is underlain by impermeable rock formation of the Upper Jurassic. A great proportion of the scanty rainfall that runs as a surface stream, sinks through the permeable gravel of the Wadi bed and is retained by the underlying impermeable rock formation. Water held in the Wadi bed is drained off by the pumping station of Al Ha'ir, 32 kms. south of Al Riyadh.

Al Ha'ir Basin is 544 metres above sea-level; so it is 50 meters lower than Al Riyadh. The sloping southward strata help to make this basin the accumulative area of the ground water of Wadi Hanifah and its tributaries north of Al Ha'ir. Wadi Hanifah reaches this basin after it has been enriched by the waters of its chief tributary Al Aysan, and its feeders, from the north; and the Wadis of Al Ammariyah, Wubair, Al Qaddiyah, Numar and Sha'ibā from the west.

The water of Al Ha'ir pumping station reaches the town through pipes of 8 inches diameter; it is stored in two huge cement reservoirs, one in Eleishah and the other in Al Shemeisy. The capacity of storage in each is 3 million gallons. The analysis of Al Ha'ir's water is as follows⁽¹⁾.

Ions	Units par million
Sodium	34
Calcium	83
Magnesium	38
Sulphate	150
Chloride	64
Carbonate	—
Bicarbonate	322
Total Salinity	701

These figures show that the water is quite suitable for drinking as salinity is only 701 ppm.

Such water bearing strata are very small in extent as they depend on the scanty rainfall in recent times; so they could not possibly cover,

⁽¹⁾ Al Riyadh Municipality: *Al Riyadh during the Reign of King Saoud*. Al-Riyadh, 1962, p. 43.

for a long time, the needs of agriculture as well as the daily consumption of water, in modern Riyadh, which is roughly estimated as 7 million gallons a day. The natural result has asserted itself; as the water drained is gradually diminishing. The amount of water has decreased from 5 million gallons a day in the first year of pumping to 2 million gallons a day in the year 1962.

The second locality of pumping is in Wadi Numar, one of the tributaries of Wadi Hanifah; the confluence of the two Wadis is at the southern end of the town. This source of water is much poorer than the former; and its daily production is nearly 1 million gallons a day. The water of Numar pumping station is stored in a huge cement reservoir in Manfuhah; its capacity is 3 million gallons. This reservoir supplies the south districts of Al Riyadh with water. The salinity of its water is not different from that of the Ha'ir.

The former two localities cannot possibly suffice the daily requirements of the modern town which is spreading out extensively. So the future of the town would be at stake, if these water bearing strata were the only source of water. They may be of considerable value to a nomadic pattern of life, but they are entirely incapable of supplying a modern town that accomodates tens of thousands of people who adopted a modern pattern of life.

The most important source of water lies in a huge reservoir, hundreds of metres thick. Water has been stored in this huge basin during former geologic epochs of rainy climates. The lower Jurassic sandstone, below Riyadh region, forms rich water bearing strata. This aquifer which is called the Minjur sandstone⁽¹⁾ was tackled in the year 1960. Four wells of 800 metres depth give nearly 5 million gallons a day. These deep wells which are located in different districts in Al Riyadh, are as follows: one is pierced near the military academy, the second is in Al Milaz, the third lies in Jaz'ah and the fourth is located in Al Shemeisy. Their water is more saline than that of both Al Ha'ir and Numar; the analysis of water has proved a salinity estimated at 1090 parts per million. This means that the water is still usable.

⁽¹⁾ The International Bank for Reconstruction and Development: *Economic Development in Saudi Arabia* (In Arabic); November 1960, pp. 30-32.

It is needless to say that these four deep wells supply the town with most of its water needs as it will be clearly seen from the forthcoming table. The Minjur aquifer which has not yet been fully used, guarantees the future requirements of the town.

The total amount of water produced from the different resources is estimated at 7.8 million gallons per day; this quantity covers the present water needs of the town. The following table shows the production of the different resources ⁽¹⁾.

The District	Amount of water
1. Al Ha'ir Pumping Station	2,160,000 gallons per day
2. Numar Pumping Station	864,000 » » »
3. The deep well of the Military Academy	1,152,000 » » »
4. The deep well of Gaz'ah	1,728,000 » » »
5. The deep well of Al Milaz	648,000 » » »
6. The deep well of Al Shemeisy	<u>1,296,000</u> » » »
Total production	<u><u>7,848,000</u></u>

4. CLIMATE.

Temperature :

The chief features are the high temperature of summer, and the cold temperature of winter specially during the night. Both annual and diurnal ranges are wide. Clear skies are the main factor in developing intense heating particularly in a dry desert region.

The following table throws a light in the temperature of al Riyadh; it is the means of 10 years data, from 1952 to 1961 ⁽²⁾.

⁽¹⁾ Al Riyadh Municipality : *op. cit.*, p. 47.

⁽²⁾ Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, Ministry of Defence, Department of Civil Aviation : *Meteorological Reports for the years 1952-1961.*

Monthly Av.		Mean Daily Max.		Mean Daily Min.		Diurnal range		Max. Hst		Min. Lst		Annual Range
Jan.	July	Jan.	July	Jan.	July	Jan.	July	Jan.	July	Jan.	July	
15	36	21	42	10	26	11	16	29	44	1	23	11

In winter, the average temperature is 15° C.; the mean daily maximum is 21° C., and the mean daily minimum is 10° C. These figures give a clear idea about the wide range between day and night; the days are somewhat warm, as the sun rays under a clear sky, naturally cause warmth. But the nights are very cold and the temperature usually falls to 1° C.; sometime the temperature falls below the freezing point. So it was not strange to hear that one of the soldiers who kept guard during the night was found dead of cold during the winter of 1964.

In summer, the mean daily maximum temperature rises to 42° C., and the mean daily minimum falls to 26° C. The diurnal range is very wide during this season. This fact shows that the days have very high temperature. The rays of the midday sun, beating on the barren ground, make the sand so hot that it seems to scorch even shod feet. The air is heated by conduction and a shimmering heat haze is set up; the differential refraction in the heated layers resulting in the mirage. The Simoom, fairly frequent in this season in Al Riyadh region, laden with dense clouds of blistering sand through which it is impossible to see more than a few yards, has a very bad effect on the inhabitants, particularly on foreigners. The nights are distinctly cool; after sunset the heat is quickly lost by radiation and the temperature falls rapidly.

The summer type of climate reflects its bearings on man, plant, and buildings. The type of clothes, dressed by the Arabs, has its relationship to the prevailing weather. The wide dress (Al Jalabiah) helps ventilating the body and lessening the amount of perspiration. Those who are dressed in western clothes would greatly appreciate the more convenient Arab dress. The head dress (the Ghutra) helps to shade the head and protect the face from the scorching sandy winds.

The old clay buildings were designed within the sphere of this type of climate. Windows are restricted to very narrow openings in the walls either circular or rectangular. Such a device would keep the rooms cool and free from the scorching heat outside. Also the sun dried bricks are more suitable than the cement bricks in the modern buildings as they do not absorb the heat of the sun.

The high temperature is a great strain on the nerves of the inhabitants who feel as if strangled by it; so they could not but sleep in the open during the night; they either sleep on their house roofs or go outside the town and sleep in the cafés scattered around the town in the open air. The green carpet of coarse grass in gardens or in patches around the town became parched, brown and brittle, so that it is blown away by the wind.

It may be useful to note the contrast with other towns such as Jiddah and Cairo. Jiddah which enjoys the tempering influence of the sea, has a warm winter and the temperature rarely falls down to 18° C. Also in summer, the weather is temperate, and the temperature rarely rises above 38° C. Cairo which is far away from the sea, has a mean daily minimum in January 17° C.; thus it is much warmer than Riyadh. In summer, the mean daily maximum is 36° C. The wide difference between the two towns ascertains the desert type climate of Al Riyadh.

Humidity is generally low, but a marked increase occurs in winter. Low humidity together with high temperature in summer makes living conditions bearable. If the high temperature in summer were accompanied by high humidity, life would be extremely unpleasant. The mean relative humidity in January is 54 per cent, but in July it falls down to 17%, and the lowest minimum is only 6%. These figures show the dryness of the desert climate of Al Riyadh Region.

The prevailing winds are the north and north western winds; the south and south-east winds are of a few occurrences.

Rainfall is exceedingly variable in amount from year to year. The rainfall in 1952 was 6 mm., but the amount of rains rose the following year 1953 to 227 mm. The mean annual rainfall is 26 mm. The rainy season begins in November and ends in May; February and March are the rainiest months. A great deal of rain may fall in a short time, 25 mm. per hour is by no means unusual; but during the rest of the month, the sky is clear and rainless.

Historical Evolution :

In the 13th century, Yakut Al Hamawy does not mention Al Riyadh in his book «Mojam Al Buldan»; perhaps it was such a small hamlet that it could not draw his attention. Niebhur ⁽¹⁾, in the 18th century, did not write about it when he was numerating the villages of Najd. The big oasis villages overshadowed the very small ones of which Al Riyadh was one.

Manfuhah which is only now a small suburb of Al Riyadh was a village of considerable size that impressed the Arab and European writers because of the leadings part it was playing at that time. Al Dir'iyah which was an important village too was a strong rival to Manfuhah; and each of them waged war against each other. Al Riyadh which is situated between these two powerful villages, came frequently under the military sphere of either of them.

The Arab historian of Najd, Othman Bin Bishr ⁽²⁾ states that Al Riyadh which was governed by Diham bin Dawas, was annexed to the dominions of Al Saouds the rulers of Al Dir'iyah in the year 1187 H., 1773 A.D. After the destruction of Al Dir'iyah by the armies of Mohammad Ali in the year 1818, Al Saouds, after recovering from the disaster that befell them, regained their power under the leadership of Al Imam Turki bin Abdallah and settled in Al Riyadh which superseded Al Dir'iyah as their seat of power in the year 1240 H. ⁽³⁾ 1824 A.D. From this year on, Al Riyadh played the most important role in the history of the Arab Peninsula.

The spatial evolution of the town may be divided into three stages (Fig. 2) :

- A. During the nineteenth century.
- B. The first half of the twentieth century.
- C. The modern Riyadh.

⁽¹⁾ NIEBUHR, M., *Description de L'Arabie*. Paris, 1779, tome II, p. 203.

⁽²⁾ OTHMAN BIN BISHR; *Onwan Al Majd fi Tareekh Najd*. «The Guide of Pride in the History of Najd». Al Riyadh, 1373 H., vol. I, p. 69.

⁽³⁾ OTHMAN BIN BISHR; *op. cit.*, vol. II, p. 18.

A. *Al Riyadh in the nineteenth century :*

The old village of Al Riyadh is the nucleus round which the modern town has been extending in all directions after the fortified walls had been demolished.

One of the aged inhabitants recounted that the walls were built by Nassir Bin Hamid Bin Nasser Al A'ezî, the governor of the town during the Turkish rule after the conquest of Najd by Ibrahim Pasha. The walls, according to his description, were located as follows :

The south walls were erected south of the present Dokhna square ; on the east, the walls were parallel to the street of King Faisal ; on the north, they were bounded by Al Mousimiah and Al Azzawiah districts which lie south to Al Khazan Street ; in the west, the walls were close to the present Al Ata'if Street. Thus, the village extended 1125 metres from north to south and 750 metres from east to west. It had a rectangular shape.

This description of the walls is not far from the truth, because the old cemeteries which are still existing, but abandoned, may be considered as the signposts that give the true boundaries of the old walled village. These burial places which are close to the demolished walls are : Shalka on the north east, Jabrah on the south east, Abu Al Habag on the north, Al Megebrah on the south.

The perimeter of the walls was pierced by bastioned gates that served as an outlet to the walled palm groves encircling the village. No information was given about the right number of the gates, but the aged teller presumed that the gates might be four in number corresponding to the main four points of the compass ; the northern gate led to the track of Al Qasim, the southern one faced Manfuhah, the eastern served the track to Al Ahsa, and the western gate led to Al Hijaz.

Lorimer ⁽¹⁾, in his *Gazetteer of the Persian Gulf* recounted that the town had six gates, and its inhabitants amounted to 8000 souls.

The village embraced both settled and semi-settled patterns of life as the inhabitants who were clans from Onaizah and Tammim tribes,

(1) LORIMER, J.G., *Gazetteer of the Persian Gulf*, vol. II, Calcutta, 1908, p. 1592.

depended for their sustenance upon agriculture as well as on grazing in the surrounding tribal areas. Some of the descendants of these clans such as Al Bou Shams, Al Rayis, Al Shashat and Al Zara'a, are still living in Al Riyadh.

The most eminent feature of the morphology of the village is the central enclave embracing a cropping out limestone rock more elevated than the surrounding clay houses. This limestone platform which shelves down on all sides is called Al Safat. To the north of this enclave lies the great mosque, and the market which presents the commercial core in the village, to the south, Al Saud's palace was erected. The palace accommodated the administrative departments. This district centre includes the central services required by such inhabitants of primitive needs: mosque, shops and the governor's offices.

A wide street crossed the village from east to west passing through the central enclave and dividing the village into two sections; the southern one was twice as much as the northern section. The residential area which enclosed the central district was occupied congregationally by the different clans of tribes. The lanes which were very narrow, converge to the central core from the farther ends of the village.

Palgrave's description, after his controversial visit to Al Riyadh in the year 1862, differs in many points from the previously stated description.

Palgrave ⁽¹⁾ claims that Al Riyadh is of square shape with two main streets, one running from north to south and the other extending from east to west. The two arteries intersected in the central square and divided the village into four distinctive quarters. In the north east quarter lived the royal family and other rich families. The south west division was occupied by the descendents of Al Sheikh, the religious leaders. In the north west section resided the political and religious outcasts. The last quarter was reserved for the poor families (Fig. 3).

Any one who knows about Islamic principles and the tribal inherited traditions that admits of no racial or social distinctions, will never believe that the religious society in that primitive village was living in segregated

⁽¹⁾ PALGRAVE, W.G., *Une année de voyage dans l'Arabie Centrale 1862-1863*. Paris 1866, tome second, pp. 47-49.

segments. From the economic view point, there was no wide difference among the inhabitants who discharge agricultural and pastoral tasks. Certainly there were poor labourers who were either of tribal descent or slaves; the former lived in the neighbourhood of their kinsmen, the

FIG. 3.

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|-------------------------|------------------------------------|
| 1. — Market. | 6. — Poor class quart. |
| 2. — Faisal's places. | 7. — Religious dissidents quarter. |
| 3. — Covered gallery. | 8. — Royal quarter. |
| 4. — Mosque. | 9. — Principal gate. |
| 5. — Al Cheikh quarter. | 10-19. — Other gates. |

latter lived with their masters or near them. The presence of any political or religious outcasts could not be conceived as there were neither political parties nor different religious sects. In a narrow scaled society such as Al Riyadh, the rich and poor lived side by side. The people too, had to live in complete unity as their strength lay in their unity; in such case they will be able to defend themselves against the attacks of their enemies and they could wage war against neighbours and acquire booty.

Thus, Palgrave's description of Al Riyadh and its four quarters does not apply to that village in the nineteenth century.

B. *The first half of the Twentieth Century :*

For three decades, Al Riyadh did not see any radical changes; the kernel and the integuments were still within the old fortified walls. The only changes that could be observed, were related to the walls and gateways.

The old walls and their fortifications, particularly the north and east sides which were demolished by Ibn Al Rasheed at the end of the nineteenth century, were rebuilt by King Abd El Aziz Al Saoud after he had recaptured Al Riyadh after 1902.

Philby who visited Al Riyadh in the year 1917, gave the following description of the walls and gateways after they had been rebuilt ⁽¹⁾.

« The city is completely encircled by a thick wall of coarse sun-backed mud-bricks, about twenty five feet in height and surrounded by a fringe of plain sharks' teeth design; at frequent intervals its continuity is interrupted by imposing bastions and less pretensions guard-turrets, circular for the most part and slightly tapering towards the top but some few square or rectangular, varying from thirty to forty feet in height and generally projecting slightly outwards from the wall line for greater facility of defence».

He also states that the walls were pierced in nine places by gateways; the most important were, the Thumairi on the east, the Dhuhaira and Shamsiyah on the north, the Bud'ia and Muraigib on the west, the Dokhna on the south. The chief street ran from Al Thumairi on the east side to Al Bud'ia on the west side through the central enclave, and there was a branch going off from it at right angles to al Dhahaira gate on the north side. Other narrow streets led from the central enclave to the other gate ways (Fig. 4).

Philby roughly reckoned the superficial area of the village as 100 acres; but according to the recent map of Al Riyadh, the area of the old village amounts to 200 acres or less than one square kilometre.

Philby's plan of Al Riyadh is, to a great extent, inapplicable to the town of 1917, because it gave the town a triangular shape of so many

⁽¹⁾ PHILBY, H., St. J.B., *The Heart of Arabia*. London, 1922, vol. I, pp. 70-72.

dental sides. If one asks why the people of Al Riyadh exerted themselves and erected so many sided walls as there are no geographical hindrances that would oblige them to increase their hardlabour and build these denticular walls, no satisfactory explanation would be given. Philby

FIG. 4.

in that remote time, as one thinks, lacked the accurate means of drawing the right plan of Al Riyadh. The information given by the aged people of Al Riyadh proved that the old walls of the village were nearly straight.

Al Rihani ⁽¹⁾ who visited Al Riyadh later added nothing new.

⁽¹⁾ RIHANI, A., *Ibn Saoud of Arabia*. London, 1928, pp. 126-132.

After the year 1930, the process of change began, as Al Riyadh was gradually transformed into townscape with urban development. After King Abd El Aziz had ended his campaigns for the conquest and unification of the regions that formed his kingdom, peace and security spread every where his realm. Thus the people of Riyadh no longer sought security in walls; in the meantime they felt sure that concentration of habitation within the fortified walls in spite of their natural increase in number would make them suffer diseases because of lack of sanitation. So the walls succumbed to the pressure of the advancing masons and were levelled to the ground.

All around the fortified walls of Al Riyadh, except towards the north east where the cemetery of Shalka is located, lay the dense palm groves and gardens. The big gardens had famous names that are still existing as names of districts in the modern town. Al Wusaita palm grove lay to south east side, Al Shamsiyah and Al Hautah palm groves lay to the north side, Al Badia palm grove extended to the west side and Al Feryan palm grove to the south side.

This green belt which, once encompassed the old village, was sacrificed to provide an ample area for the substantial extension of the new town. King Abd El Aziz moved out of the old village into a new castellated palace called Al Murabba (Quadrangle) $1\frac{1}{2}$ klms. to the north of the old walls in the year 1938. On the east bank of Al Bat'ha channel, a large suburb was growing up to meet the needs of a new element of the population, the drivers and mechanics from different Moslim countries to look after the royal garage in the same suburb, as well as the other motor cars and lorries owned by the rich people of Al Riyadh.

The members of the royal family, the indigenious elements and the immigrants from other parts of the kingdom built their homes around the demolished walls. So the expansion of the town went in all directions. The most important point is that the expanding town continued to preserve the character of the core; *i.e.* the houses were built of clay and after the traditional architecture of the old village. This will make a wide difference between the town expansion before the year 1950 and after. The expansion after the year 1950 is distinctive because it has mostly been modelled after western architectural designs.

The Kernel expansion, in the second stage, covered an area nine times as much the old walled village; the extension is 3.5 kms. from north to south and 2.6 kms. from east to west.

Al Murabba palace presents the farthestmost northern extension, the palace of Abd Allah ibn Abd Al Rahman, the brother of the late King Abd El Aziz is the southern limit. The extension eastward is about three quarters of a kilometer east of the torrent bed of Wadi Al Bat'ha; where the suburbs of Hillet Al Abeed, Hillet Al Kosman (relating to Al Qasim), and Hillet Al Kuwaitieh have been built. In these suburbs the residential areas are intermingling with the workshops and commercial shops. The western expansion towards Wadi Hanifah is extensive.

If the expansion in this stage is applied to the present map of Al Riyadh, the streets that limit the extension will be as follows: the street of Al Washm on the north, the streets of Al Andalus and Ali Ibn Abi Taleb on the west; the intersection of Hillet Al Abeed and Al Margab denotes the eastern limitation of the expansion; the palm groves of Al Rayyis and Al Faryan, and the palace of Abd Allah Ibn Abd El Rahman on the south.

The expansion as a whole took the shape of an irregular squared figure if the node of Al Murabba is excluded. That is because the rocky tableland of Zahrat Al Wisham to the east of it, blocked the expansion of buildings in that direction, also to the west of Al Murabba, there was an unoccupied area that did not attract people to dwell in, at least in that epoch. Therefore, if Al Murabba is included, the expansion took the shape of a rough triangular figure.

On the whole, the outward extension of the town formed a ring round the kernel.

The kernel has undergone a fine degree of readjustment to a complex variety of considerations, so the internal changes were very necessary to adapt the old forms to new uses. Replacement of old buildings by new ones, specially constructed for new functions has been in process. The Old palace, near the central enclave, was levelled to the ground, and replaced by a huge building housing the law-courts, the offices of the governor of Al Riyadh province, and spacious audience chambers for the use of the King on ceremonial occasions. The great mosque too,

in its vicinity, and a large area of houses around it were demolished, and in their place arose the new mosque with its two tall minarets and graceful colonnades.

The houses bordering the crooked narrow streets and lanes were demolished to give place to new wide tarmac streets suitable for motor traffic. Modern shops lined the new streets radiating from the central enclave in every direction. So the residential belt in the kernel was invaded by the expanding commercial core and other central services.

C. *Modern Riyadh* :

The year 1950, was the dawn of prosperity in the kingdom. The oil had, of course, been found in Al Ahsa, but its exploitation had been severely limited by the requirements of allied war policy. It was not until 1950 that the first substantial dividends were to find their way into the kingdom's treasury. The following year, the royalties were double the previous year, and the dividends have been steadily increasing year after year. The following table clarifies the economic status before 1950 and after it.

Year	The income from oil in million dollars
1946	10.4
1950	56.7
1951	113.6
1952	210.7

So, it is needless to say that the economic status has been greatly improved, and the wealth derived from oil has created a desire for comfort among the people of Al Riyadh, so they have become accustomed to build luxurious villas and mansions in far away suburbs. The motor car is a powerful agent in the process of change in the modern Riyadh.

The railway between Al Dammam on the Arab Gulf and Al Riyadh began to operate in October 1951. Thus, the economic position in Al Riyadh has been improved out of all recognition by the drop in the cost of transport of all essential commodities. The railroad had transported hundreds of thousands of tons of cement, steel, tile, marble for the construction of modern office buildings, up to date apartment

houses, family residences as well as power and water plants. This material was followed by electrical equipment, sanitation and plumbing supplies, roofing materials and the hundreds of various items which enter into the demand of today's architecture. The impact of the modern railroad upon the ancient inland town, Al Riyadh has been one of the important factors in the modernization of the town.

The new paved roads which connect Al Riyadh with the other important centres in the kingdom have accelerated the growth of the town as the motor transport on these roads attracted the indigenous elements from the other regions of the kingdom as well as visitors from all parts of the world in such numbers as to outstrip the capacity of the traditional guest rite arrangements. To provide accommodation for them, hotels, restaurants, and other facilities have come into being. It is needless to say that the air traffic has added to the urbanization of the town.

In the year 1957, government offices have been transferred from Jiddah to Al Riyadh. Thousands of buildings have been constructed to accommodate the new comers. The size of the central services, commercial business and manufacturing activities has increased to cover the needs of the new society.

If Griffith Taylor's viewpoint about the stages of growth of towns is to be considered, Al Riyadh definitely passed the third stage of adolescence and is on its way to early maturity.

After considering the important factors that have led to the later growth and modernization of Al Riyadh, the axes that controlled the chief extension of buildings should be dealt with. Al Riyadh extends 12 kms. from north to south and 8 kms. from east to west; it covers superficial area of 96 square kls. The paved roads from certain locations to the kernel are the chief axes along which the expansion has taken place. On the north, the airport 9 kms. far from the kernel, determines the northward extension; on the east the railway station and the horse racing field (Al Milaz) 4.4 kms. from the kernel, orient the extension. Wadi Hanifah and Badia Palace 3.6 kms., control the extension to the west. Al Mansuriah Palace (related to Prince Mansour, King Saoud's son 12.5 kms. and Manfuhah lead the expansion to the south. These locations contribute to the orientation of the outer growth of Al Riyadh which in this stage, takes nearly a lobster like shape.

The extension takes three phases ; firstly the buildings that align the former paved roads and thoroughfares ; secondly the residential suburbs that have sprung adjacent to some of the former locations ; thirdly the infilling of the void spaces.

1. *First type extension.*

Government offices, hospitals, hotels, and institutions align the road leading to the airport. Administrative offices, schools, nursing homes, the university and residential buildings align the road leading to the race course (Al Milaz). Manufacturing shops, and some industrial plants were built on the road leading to the railway station. Dwellings run parallel to the road leading to Nasiriyah Palace.

2. *Second type of expansion.*

The suburb of Al Riyadh Al Jadidah (the New Riyadh) is a huge residential area where the officials of the ministries recently transferred from Jiddah live. This new suburb lies adjacent to the race course (Al Milaz). Shopping and central services are among the tracts of housing.

The royal Quarter forms a magnificent residential suburb around the Nasiriyah Palace. Mansions and estates face wide roads of dual carriageway, divided by an island of flower beds.

On the southern outskirts of Al Riyadh lies the big residential suburb of Al Badiyah town where the Bedouins live.

Westward expansion to Wadi Hanifah takes the form of a peripheral growth to the west of the kernel ; there are clusters of homes interspersed with open spaces.

3. *Third type Growth.*

Apartment buildings and villas that have been built or in the process of construction are filling in the breaks in the continuity of the built up area ; so a long time will not be elapsed before the agglomeration and coalescence of the separate nuclei will come to existence.

The kernel and the surrounding integuments have undergone many changes. Many old clay houses were demolished to give way either to

wide straight streets that tie the outskirts with the central core, or for new business premises. The commercial core has spread beyond the limits of the kernel; the modern shops lining the new streets form the extended arms of the commercial business in the old town.

The modern Riyadh has taken the full urban status, there exists the group of services necessary for urbanized life. Shopping centres with a full range of specialized retail services, health services such as hospitals, nursing homes and private clinics, educational services such as, secondary schools, technical institutions, public libraries, higher schools of engineering and teaching, the University with its four faculties, colleges dealing with the Arabic language and Islamic legislation under the supervision of Al Sheikh, all of these services are localized in different parts of the town. Also football fields with grandstands, recreational centres, such as the Zoo and public gardens, accommodation facilities such as first class hotels and restaurants. All these services have come to being. The network of water pipes and the gigantic electric plant were among the requirements of the modern town that have been introduced.

Physiognomical Aspects.

The town is geographically divided into eight administrative quarters; the central core forms the nucleus quarter off which branch three quarters extending to the west, east and south west. The further suburbs make the other four peripheral quarters. These quarters are characteristically different in their morphological and functional structure.

I. — THE CORE ⁽¹⁾.

The core embraces most of the old walled village, or the kernel; it is confined on the east by the street of Al Zahirah, on the west by Al Atayef

⁽¹⁾ The following description and analysis of the core and the other quarters is the result of an intensive personal field survey.

Street, on the north by the street of Al Khazzan, on the south by Dokhna district. It has undergone drastic changes by potent centrifugal and centripetal processes and the concomitant internal re-arrangement and re-adjustment. The core has admittedly been reshaped to keep pace with the broadening out prosperous town.

The central enclave is still the square of Al Safat, but greatly enlarged with flower bedded parks in the centre. Many wide paved roads branch off from this central enclave in every direction, so the old clay houses were sacrificed to the benefit of the new arrangement. The most salient feature is the entourage of the square, the great rebuilt mosque on the north, the administrative and local government buildings comprising the Principality of Al Riyadh and the royal audience chambers on the south. Four sectors make up the core. The native old market in the middle, the administrative offices and law courts amidst the market area, the modern market on the east and north; the old and new residential area contiguous to and enclosing the markets.

(a) *The native old market.*

On a grid pattern, every trade is allocated a special block. In the extreme south west of the market stands the green grocery and fruit market; butchers quarters occupy the Juxtaposition. To the south east stands the cloth market and nearby the crockery and house utensils market to have their stand. Cashiers occupy the south side of the central enclave. On the west of the market the tea, coffee and spices market lie contiguous to the wholesale market. The auction sale market (Al Harag) occupies the northern part of the market and the carpet market is close to it.

(b) *The modern market.*

The modern shops line the wide streets of the core, especially those on the north and east of the core, in a specialised pattern. The big stores with different departments specially clothes and cosmetics occupy the eastern part of the core; electric equipments extend to the south east

of the central enclave. The commercial shops and agencies in both markets amount to 1714 in number, and they occupy 501 buildings equal to 26% of the total buildings ⁽¹⁾.

(c) *Administrative buildings.*

Amid the market area and surrounding it, the administrative buildings such as the principality of Al Riyadh, Passport offices, law courts, the committee of « Al Amr Bil Ma'arouf Wal Nahy an Al Monkar » inducement to do good and avoiding the evil doings, are all Juxtaposed.

(d) *The residential area.*

The buildings of the residential area represent 74% of the total buildings in the core; the rest is occupied by the establishments of commercial activities. In spite of the many houses that were raised down to earth, the old clay houses with narrow lanes are still the dominant feature, and they form 86% of the total buildings of the core. The new buildings built of cement blocks on modern basis of architecture only represent 14% of the total buildings. The ratio of families housed in clay buildings to those living in cement modern architectural houses is 5 : 1. The dwellings and the commercial shops intermingle in the market area; this intrusive feature shows obvious signs of residential deterioration in the central part of the core. The other residential areas enclose the market area. Private clinics and pharmacies tend to be scattered with the residential area.

The majority of the old conservative families living in old clay houses sensed the importance and convenience of using the new modern devices so they installed the water and electricity supplied by the municipality. Only 210 houses out of 1228, that have not enjoyed the advantages of utilising the water and electricity services; 880 dwellings have water and electricity facilities, 51 houses have only water, 87 houses have

⁽¹⁾ Ministry of Finance : *Report on Population and Establishments in Al Riyadh* (in Arabic). Al Riyadh, 1963.

N.B. — The different figures concerning the population and buildings in the different quarters are taken from the previous report.

only electricity. These aspects reveal an important geographical feature, the fanatic people of the old Riyadh who were strictly against the introduction of the new modern devices, have changed their opinion and began to give up the old ideas and welcome the economic and social changes in order to keep pace with other progressive countries.

II. — THE INTEGUMENTS.

1. QUARTER ONE.

This administrative quarter lies to the east of the core and includes the eastern part of the kernel with the addition of the new suburbs of Hillet Al Abeed and Al Margub ; moreover it extends to the extreme east end of the town where the road to Al Kharj marks the eastern boundaries of Al Riyadh. This integument is bounded by Al Zahirah street and King Faisal Street on the west, Al Imam Faisal and Al Imam Abd El-Rahman Bin Faisal on the north, the quarters 3 and 8 on the south.

Two sectors make up this quarter. The eastern part of the kernel on the west bank of Al Bat'ha and the outer expansion on its eastern bank.

(a) *The Eastern part of the kernel.*

Two outstanding features are apparent in this portion of the kernel : firstly, the old clay houses transversed by very narrow zigzag lanes around the gigantic palace of Al Masmac which was built of clay by Abd Allah Bin Faisal Bin Turki at the end of the nineteenth century, this huge castle commemorates the triumph of King Abd El Aziz at the conquest of Al Riyadh in the year 1902 and secondly, the new apartment buildings and houses of western architecture which line the new paved wide roads, and hide behind them the former old houses. This subdivision consists of the modern market and the residential areas.

The market is the eastern extension of the commercial core ; the trades are not allocated after a specialized pattern, modern groceries stand by the stores of cloths and ready made clothes, and those lie adjacently to electric equipment shops, furniture stores and hairdressers and bookshops. These shops line the streets of Al Thumairi and King

Faisal; Syrians, Lebanese, Palestenians dominate many trades, especially groceries and the craft of hair-dressing, carpentry, butchering and bakery. To the east, a bloc is occupied by carpentries. Private clinics, pharmacies, banks, commercial agencies and other key services are linked in function to the market (fig. 5).

The residential area comprises the old clay houses and the new dwellings of western architecture; the clay houses are situated to the west of the new apartment buildings lining King Faisal Street. The new residential belt intermingle with the new modern commercial premises and some of the new blocks lie to the west of King Faisal Street.

(b) *The eastern outer expansion.*

The majority of the buildings, in these suburbs (Hillet Al Abeed and Al Margab) are built of clay during the first half of the twentieth century; moreover the architecture adhered to the old traditional pattern, only the buildings which mostly take the form of apartments, have been recently built on the eastern bank of Al Bat'ha or King Saoud Street. Big stores, travel agencies, hotels, schools, pharmacies bookshops concentrate in the modern residential area. The old residential area, which stands to the east of the modern buildings, embraces a limited number of commercial premises.

Three cemeteries are located in this quarter, but they are now abandoned, the biggest and the oldest is Shalqa cemetery extending to the west of King Faisal Street, the second lies towards east of the former street, the third extends in the suburbs of Hillet Al Abeed.

The residential buildings of this quarter represent 84% of the total buildings, the rest is occupied by establishments of commercial activities. This percentage nearly agrees with the ratio of clay buildings to modern cement buildings, *i.e.* the commercial establishments are totally housed in modern new buildings. In general the number of buildings is more than twice as big as the core, but the number of the commercial premises is far less than the core.

The number of dwellings and premises supplied with water and electricity is equal to those which do not utilise these facilities.

Fig. 5.

	GREEN GROCERIES		WATCHES
	BUTCHERS		JEWELRY & GOLDSMITH
	GRAIN DEALERS		HAIRDRESSERS
	BAKERY & RESTAURANTS		CARPENTRIES
	MODERN GROCERIES		WORKSHOPS
	GROCERIES		BANKS
	TEA, COFFEE & SPICES		CASHIERS
	WHOLESALE MARKET		PHARMACIES
	MOTOR CAR SPARE PARTS		CARPETS & AUCTION SALE
	CLOTH & READY MADE CLS.		VARIOUS KINDS OF TRADES
	TAILORS		GOVERNMENT BUILDINGS
	STORES		MOSQUE
	HOUSE UTENSILS & CROCKERY		RESIDENTIAL AREA
	LIBRARIES		
	FURNITURE		
			SANITARY EQUIPMENTS
			ELECTRIC

2. QUARTER FOUR.

This quarter lies to the east of Al Bat'ha bank and is confined by : Omar bin Al Khattab Street on the north, Abd Al Rahman bin Faisal on the south and the road of Al Kharj on the east. Its characteristics make it individually distinct among the other quarters. The areal allocation of the different sectors is conspicuous. Three sectors make up this quarter : the market, the central station of motor cars and their mechanic engineering business, and the residential area.

The market : The forefront of the market which faces Al Bat'ha bed (King Saoud Street) is made up of modern buildings the ground floors of which are mostly occupied by commercial premises. The native market where every trade is allocated, a special block extends adjacently eastward of the former belt. It is named Al Kuweitieh market (Market of Kuwait).

The market is the extension of the commercial centre in the core and its branch in the former quarter. The native market is characterized by exclusive minute specialization : cotton and silk cloth trade and ready made clothes occupy the eastern block in the market ; tailors are Juxtaposed. Crockery trade, specially the old traditional utensils, lies to the east of the first block. Amidst the two trades, carpet trade has its place. Spices and grain dealers occupy the northern part of the market. Butchers, green grocers, date traders, and herbage dealers are all Juxtaposed.

The Industrial Sector : The central motor car and bus station is located on the north sector of this quarter ; it is the terminal station for all roads coming from different parts of the kingdom : from Jiddah, Mecca, and Al Madinah in Al Hijaz, from Al Dhahran and Al Hofuf in the eastern province, from Al Qassim on the north, and from Al Aflag on the south. In the environs of this station lie all spare parts shops and mechanical engineering workshops. Also in this sector (Hillet Al Ghorabi) used motor cars are exhibited and the exhibition parks occupy a large area. Establishments both commercial and industrial outnumber those in the core or in quarter I ; they count 2131 which is nearly equal to both premises in the core and quarter I. This shows that commercial activities

and key services spread out from the core to the former quarter in order to meet the increasing needs of the flourishing town.

The Residential Area : In the market and industrial areas, houses intermingle with the commercial premises and workshops to the east of these commercial and industrial areas, the residential area forms an extensive block. On the extreme east huts and tents spread dispersively to house the poor immigrant Bedouins.

The majority of buildings, as they are mostly the product of the first expansion, are built of clay and represent 81% of the total buildings while the modern new houses are only 12% of the total, the huts and tents constitute the rest (fig. 6).

The buildings supplied with water and electricity facilities, in this quarter, are 56% of the total buildings; those which are deprived of these facilities are 27%; some of the buildings are connected with only waterpipes, others are only wired for electricity, they are successively 10%, 6%. This shows that utilization of water and electricity facilities is spreading fast in this desert town (Fig. 7).

3. QUARTER FIVE.

This quarter extends from the core westward to Wadi Hanifah; it is confined by Al Atayif street on the east, Al Khazzan Street on the north, Al Kura and Al Badiyah Streets (Khalid bin Al Walid Street and Al Yarmūk Street) on the south.

Two sectors make up this quarter; the eastern sector, limited by Al Shemeisy Hospital Street (Al Imam Abd El Aziz bin Mohammad Street) on the west, represents a connected block of residential area with mainly clay buildings and clusters of commercial premises. The western sector which forms the outer margin of expansion, is a residential belt of modern buildings modelled on western patterns with void spaces in between.

The clay buildings of this quarter make 89.5% of the total buildings; only 9% is built of cement blocks, the huts and tents of the poor Bedouins exist at the periphery and form 1.5% of the total.

Buildings enjoying these facilities are 60% of the total, while the percentage not connected with the water and electric plants is 23%.

FIG. 6.

Fig. 7.

Houses connected with electricity form 7% of the total, and those supplied with water pipes are 9% of the total.

4. QUARTER THREE.

This quarter branches off the core southwestward to Wadi Hanifah, it is confined by King Faisal Street on the east, and quarter five on the north. It is characterised by its clay buildings which form 91% of the total buildings; the huts and tents at the periphery make up 5% of the total. This means that the only modern buildings which spread only in the eastern sector, if the palaces of Prince Abd Allah bin Abd El Rahman (the King's uncle) are excluded, are only 4% of the total; some commercial shops exist among the tracts of houses especially in the eastern sector. Very few voids are seen amidst the built areas.

The working class and the native poor families of the Old Riyadh whose houses were demolished are housed in this quarter; moreover the immigrants from other parts of Najd also live in this quarter.

Only 46% of the houses are supplied with water and electricity facilities; 35% are not connected with either water or electric plants: dwellings that enjoy only water facilities are 11% of the total, the rest are only supplied with electricity facilities.

5. QUARTER EIGHT.

This residential suburb has been recently built in the further south east of the town. It houses the settled nomads and other immigrants from many parts of Najd. Although the houses have been recently built after the year 1950, their style is neither similar to the western pattern nor to the old traditional Najdi style. They still preserve the eastern taste but are more developed than the old traditional houses. This suburb is named Manfuhah Al Jadidah (new Manfuhah).

The clay buildings form 93% of the total buildings. The rest is divided between the huts and cement dwellings. Only 16% of the houses are supplied with water and electricity, but the majority are deprived of these facilities. This shows that the newly settled Bedouins are either too poor to utilize these facilities or they have not yet developed, the taste of using them.

6. QUARTER SIX OR THE ROYAL QUARTER.

The royal quarter is located to the northwest of the town; it extends from the west bank of Bat'ha bed on the east to Wadi Hanifah on the west, and lies to the north of both the core and quarter 5. It occupies a wide area more than $1/5$ of the superficial area of the town, but it includes the least number of buildings. That is because the mansions of the royal members and rich people with gardens around occupy wide areas. Moreover there are vast void areas amidst these mansions, government buildings and the other ordinary clay houses.

The scenery is very impressive and attractive as the avenues and wide roads are lined with ornamental trees with islands in the centre; there are also many public parks and gardens such as Al Murabba and Al Futa. This quarter includes many governmental building such as Kasr Al Hamraa which houses the offices and minister's council, schools, hospitals and other administrative buildings.

It is interesting to notice the contrast between the magnificent and most beautiful mansions and villas with the clay houses in their environs and the huts at their periphery. This salient feature; *i.e.* mansions lie side by side with huts and clay houses, gives a concrete example of the democracy of Islam; there are no differences among the poor and the rich, all are alike; the poor are not excluded from the royal quarter.

7. QUARTER SEVEN.

This quarter extends to the north and northeast of the town; it lies north to both the royal quarter and quarter 4; the hilly escarpments border it on the east and the west, on the north lies the airport. Two sectors make this quarter: government buildings and the residential suburb of the New Riyadh.

The different ministry buildings, military barracks and the military academy and the hospital line King Saoud street. Also, first class hotels such as Al Yammama and Sahara Palace are located in the same sector; to the extreme north lies the airport.

The residential suburb : The New Riyadh, extends to the east of the former sector. It is newly built to house government officials and their families who are transferred from Jiddah. The zoo lies to the east of the suburb, the horse race course; Municipal Hall, and the University of Al Riyadh are all Juxtaposed at the periphery of this suburb. Al Milaz street which connects this suburb with the town is a wide two way auto-strad, divided by central islands of flower beds; this road is lined with apartment buildings, schools and villas. Some commercial premises are among the houses.

The stone and cement houses form 53% of the total buildings; this percentage is the highest if compared with the other quarters of the town. Also huts and tents make the highest percentage existing in all other quarters, they amount to 34%. The clay houses form the least percentage as they are only 13% of the total buildings. These characteristics make this quarter distinct among the other quarters of Al Riyadh.

The buildings which enjoy water and electricity facilities are 42% of the total buildings; those which do not utilize these facilities are 45% of the total. Houses connected either with water or electricity facilities are 3% and 10% successively.

POPULATION

Because of the lack of any data before the year 1963, the population of Al Riyadh was the result of guess work, either by Foreign travellers or by local authorities. The first census which has ever been taken was in the year 1962. The population was estimated at 8000 souls by Lorimer at the end of the nineteenth century; Philby's estimation in the year 1917 was 30.000. This means that the population quadrupled itself within fifty years if the former estimations were right; but the rate of the national increase especially when the high death rate is considered; never leads to such explosive results. Also, during this period the town did not receive any immigrants as its economic status was still low and Al Riyadh was suffering its maigre days. That is why the estimated figures are not reliable.

The population of Al Riyadh, according to the first official census, are 169,185 souls⁽¹⁾. This colossal figure could never be explained on the basis of the natural increase of the indigenous population of the town in forty years. Certainly the natural increase presents a part of this growth because of differences between the birth rate and the death rate which has been lowered by the improving economic conditions and the resultant rise in standards of living as well as the improving medical care and hygiene existing in the Modern Riyadh. But immigration is the most potent factor that has led to this considerable increase.

Many of the nomads, encouraged by the convenient mode of life and better chances of work, have adopted the settled life in the flourishing town. Also the immigrants, from many parts of the kingdom, from other parts of Arabia and from the Islamic countries, contributed to that increase in population. The mass transference of government employees from Jiddah adds much to the increase of population. Students, in all stages of education both secular and religious, came to the town to quench their thirst for learning. Men of business have been attracted by the unlimited opportunities of founding profitable enterprises. Moreover, professional specialists are summoned by the authorities to give their services and compensate for the shortage of the Saudi experts.

The males amount to 96,368, while the females are 72,817, with a ratio of 4 to 3. The great increase of males in relation to females indicates that many of the new comers are residing without their families who are left in their homeland. This distinctive feature is concomitant to the newly grown up towns which need a lot of manpower in the sector of services. Jiddah does not differ from Al Riyadh, as the percentage of males is 57 of the total population. But the males in Al Madinah which is lagging behind the two recently developing towns, form only 52% of the total population. The size of the family inclines to be big as 59% of the families average from 3 to 8 members each; families of one or two members constitute 18% of the total population; the rest, 23% are families of more than 9 persons.

⁽¹⁾ Ministry of Finance and National Economy : *op. cit.*, p. 13.

Distribution of Population.

Distribution of population in the different quarters is uneven; and three degrees of density are distinguished in the town.

First, the core is the least populated district as the displacement of residence by other functions and the demolition of old clay houses to give way for wide paved roads help to empty the core of its old inhabitants who are steadily decreasing during the two last decades. The core is peopled by 8623 or 5% of the total population of Al Riyadh.

Second, the four quarters contiguous to the core embrace 67% of the total population of the town. These quarters are the most densely populated in the town. Quarter 5, by itself contains as much people as the three outer quarters 6, 7, 8 altogether, so this quarter shows the highest densely populated district in Al Riyadh.

The population is distributed among the four contiguous quarters as follows (Fig. 8).

quarter 5	37740 persons
» 4	26045 »
» 3	27271 »
» 1	22596 »

If reasons are sought for such high density in the former quarters, one would say that the native inhabitants who moved out of the kernel chose the nearest area to their old living places; also it is more convenient to live by the market area in town where means of transport are neither well arranged nor developed. Moreover most of the immigrants, either the foreigners or the native elements of the kingdom, feel more secure in living in populous districts.

Third, the outer suburbs or quarters 6, 7, 8 are less populated and the houses are widely scattered, they embrace 22% of the total population of the town.

The distribution of population is as follows :

quarter 6	10510 persons
» 7	12443 »
» 8	14127 »

Fig. 8.

Economic Activities :

It is well known, in Al Riyadh, that females do not share work with males who monopolise activities both economic or official.

The males who carry out economic activities, excluding governmental business, amount to 34504 persons or 35% of the total number of males. They are distributed among the different economic activities as follows:

1. Commercial business	45 %
2. Industrial activities	23 %
3. Key Services	15 %
4. Building and construction	9 %
5. Agricultural production	4 %
6. Water and electric plants.....	3 %
7. Transport.....	0.5 %
8. Quarries and mines	0.5 %
	100 %

The previous table shows that commercial business has the lion's share of all other activities, it absorbs 45% of the total number working in non-governmental economic activities. The industrial occupation in manufacturing establishments rank second as they employ 23% of the total number of workers. Those who work in key services represent 15% of the total number; such percentage shows that the authorities in Al Riyadh pay much attention to develop services in order to keep pace with the growing population of the town. Workers in building and construction rank fourth; such a great number of building workers shows that the town is continually expanding and the government and people are constantly building. The number of farmers and farming labourers is very modest, such a feature is not strange in such desert surroundings, they only form 4% of the total number of workers.

Transport :

Local means of communication between the core and the outskirts are neither developed nor well arranged. It was not until the year 1964, when the local authorities began to conceive the importance of transport

services in the town, that a few buses began to transverse the capital through certain roads from north to south or from the airport to Manfuhah, others connect the Nasiriyah on the west and Al Milaz on the east with the core. Taxis, without any supervision or commitment from the local authorities, give their services to the passengers for changeable fares that rise or fall according to many factors such as supply and demand in some cases and competition in others.

Light goods as vegetables, fruits, groceries and seeds are conveyed by carts from the wholesale market to the retailers; heavier goods such as furniture or the like are carried by lorries. Porters play an important part in carrying goods from place to place either on their heads or on their backs.

Supply and home trade :

The agricultural hinterland of Al Riyadh embraces the oases of Wadi Hanifah and the nearby districts; the districts of Al Kharj. (84 klms. from the town), Manfuhah (4 klms.), Al Dir'iyah (15 klms.), Al Jubailah and Al Uyaynah (40 klms.), and Dhurma (85 klms.) are the main agricultural terrain that supply Al Riyadh with vegetables such as : Tomatoes, eggplant, potatoes, peas, beans, broad beans, cabbages, cauliflower, turnips, radish, carrots, spinach, okra, etc. Fruits such as watermelons, banana, citrus, pears, peach, apricot, figs, sweetmelon, grapes and dates are also cultivated in the hinterland. The agricultural districts of Al Qassim (500 klms.) such as Bureidah, Al Rass, Onaiza and Al Asiah which grow the previous kind of vegetables and fruits help to cover the local consumption of these kinds in Al Riyadh. Moreover many kinds of fruits and vegetables such as apples, grapes, oranges and potatoes are imported from Lebanon, Syria and Jordan by means of lorries via tapline road. Imported canned vegetables and fruits help to cover the local needs.

Wheat, Sorghum, millet and beans are so scantily grown, in the former districts, that they only suffice a very little portion of the local consumption which depends largely on imported articles from other Arab countries and the United States of America.

Livestock are reared every where in the hinterland of Al Riyadh and so dairies are to be seen everywhere in the environs, but their products never meet the local increasing demand for them. Thus livestock imported alive from Somalia and the neighbouring countries, butter and both condensed and evaporated milk from Denmark, cheese and eggs from the Netherlands, iced chickens and canned meat from western European countries, form the bulk of the local consumption.

Thus, if the former local products are excluded, the local consumption depends on imported goods from different countries. It is hard to sort out every imported article and the importing countries in such a little space, so only some examples will be mentioned. Rice and tea are imported from India and Ceylon; coffee from Al Yaman, Ethiopia and Somalia; spices from Malaya and Indonesia; olives and olive oil from Lebanon and Syria; sugar from Egypt, India and Aden; cloth from U. S. A., England, Japan and India; industrial machines, electric equipment, motor cars and manufactured articles from U. S. A., England, Italy and Japan; medical equipment from England, West Germany, Japan and Czechoslovakia. In a word, the local consumption and home trade depend on the imports which are easily paid for from the oil revenues.

The formerly stated items of nutrition show clearly that the people of Al Riyadh have changed their dietary habits. From a diet that used dates as the basic staple and rice as the most important supplement, the people have shifted to rice with meat as the basic food item, supplemented with a large variety of foodstuffs, mostly canned or packaged and commonly imported. Eating foreign things has become a fashionable fad in the town, as the people are encouraged by the spreading effects of the high cash wages and the prosperity resulted from oil industry.

The Process of Change : Physical and Social.

Al Riyadh, as an oasis village in the heart of Najd, was isolated and cut off from the outer world. The camel as the only means of transport did not help much in connecting the desert village with the ports on the Red Sea and the Arab Gulf; moreover this tiresome and rugged wilderness

did not encourage the foreigners to pass or contact it. Also the people who were stiff and unpolished as an outcome of the cruel desert environment, felt hatred to the foreigners who might come to them. Even in the first decades of the nineteenth century, no one visited al Riyadh except with the King's permission and all who did so were the King's guests. Thus, the people did not come under any foreign sphere of influence.

Naturally the inhabitants of Al Riyadh were strictly dominated by old traditions and religious sanctions; moreover, the limited economic conditions under which they live, did not allow any significant change in the inherited patterns of life. The resultant pattern of life existed in the town before the recent modernisation was as follows :

The house was one or two storied building of mud bricks; the plan of the house is built around religious principles, or in other words, the status of women is the pivot around which the plan of the house revolves. The main feature is the courtyard around which the rooms are built; the windows facing on this courtyard or the lane are higher than the average so that no one could see in; the low walls on the roof, the complete segregation between men's sitting rooms (Al Majlis) and women's living rooms; all these arrangements and precautions are meant to keep the women in privacy and out of men's sight. The open courtyard inside the house includes all the necessities as the privy, the kitchen, the well, the oven and lastly a stable for domestic animals, if the owner has not a stable annexed to his courtyard. The rooms are spacious, the plastered walls and doors are decorated in gaudy of colours; the ceilings which are covered in the houses of the well-to-do, with cotton cloth, contain highly embellished designs. The fireplace for making coffee in the reception room is a principal feature in the old houses of Al Riyadh.

Recently, many of the inhabitants left these old clay houses and are living now in new modern houses with sanitation facilities. Their new economic status helped them to lead a comfortable life in the new modern dwellings.

Women were rarely seen, and if they were seen at all in the market or the lanes of the old village they were covered from head to foot, but

now women from different countries wander freely in the markets and streets unveiled. Their short skirts and nylon stockings or bare legs and neat high heeled shoes were never seen before the last decade in Al Riyadh. Women of indigenous origin are still veiled, but their garments have become more revealing than those of their sisters in the old village, moreover they are more freely seen in the streets and markets than before.

The men, in the old village, would appear in public in Arab dress; and that applied both to the indigenous elements and the Muslim foreigners; but now European dress is frequently seen. Teachers, technical experts and other foreign elements wear European dress; also some of the native elements, the troops, officers, and policemen all wear European uniforms.

Such a change has been the result of the contact with foreign elements, and also the powerful influence of school teachers on the younger generation is responsible for that change.

Smoking and photographing were strictly forbidden by the religious zealots and were never allowed in public; but now smokers are seen everywhere and cigarettes are sold in public, photographers occupy shops in the most important streets. Actually, it is a revolutionarily change to have such novelties in Al Riyadh.

Magnificent motor cars take the place of the camel and the donkey too; modern cafés, luxurious hotels and restaurants, and other urban features have seen the light through only the last decade.

In a word, after the people of Al Riyadh have mixed with the immigrants from other Islamic and western countries, the tempo of the process of change has been quickened in a way that the transformation scene in the Modern Riyadh would transcend the dreams of those who saw and knew the old village of the same name. The physical and social revolution which has been the result of the oil royalties and the concomitant flow of imports and new comers, helps to develop Al Riyadh into one of the best towns in the Middle East.

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